

SATISFACTORY OR UNSATISFACTORY GUEST EXPERIENCES IN AIRBNB ACCOMMODATIONS COMPARED TO TRADITIONAL HOTELS

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Introduction

The sharing economy, also known as the collaborative economy, is based on co-creation through networks in online environments and is driven by the need for sustainability, happiness, and financial gain (Hamari, 2016; Allee, 2003; Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004; Reuschl, 2022). But even if academics and managers are becoming more interested in it, travelers choose peer-to-peer lodging rental services (henceforth referred to as P2P lodging) for some reasons or circumstances that are still unclear (Lalicic & Weismayer, 2018; Sainaghi & Baggio, 2020). According to Sainaghi and Baggio (2020), Airbnb has emerged as the most popular trend in the hotel industry and one of the most successful sharing economy models. Scholars have analyzed Airbnb's possible danger to the conventional hotel industry or come to the conclusion that it generates demand by giving travelers access to travel alternatives that they otherwise would not have had.

Additionally, Benítez-Aurioles (2019) came to the conclusion that "hotel occupancy and economic returns in Barcelona, independent of the hotel category, have been negatively affected by the expansion of the peer-to-peer market for tourist accommodation". According to Mate-Sanchez-Val (2020), "the primary threats to traditional accommodation providers are Airbnb's private rooms and the concentration of the Airbnb market in fewer hosts". Travelers may view Airbnb as a more or less ideal substitute for hotels, such as mid- or low-cost lodgings (Guttentag & Smith, 2017) or lodgings that don't cater to business travelers (Zervas, 2021).

In conclusion, prior research regarding Airbnb has not provided definitive evidence concerning its impact on the hotel sector. Consequently, given the new challenges that Airbnb poses for hotels, it remains essential to conduct a comparative analysis of both accommodation types in order to evaluate and test the distinctions between Airbnb and conventional hotels.

Distinction factors for guest preferences between Airbnb and traditional hotels

Airbnb is dedicated to facilitating access to accommodations among individuals at competitive rates (Sanchez Franco & Alonso-Dos-Santos, 2021). This business model integrates a diverse array of user-generated content into a network that generates value (Reuschl, 2022). While Airbnb has emerged as an affordable means for individuals to earn supplementary income with flexibility (Guttentag, 2015; Guttentag, 2018; Liang, 2018), the increasing availability of shared accommodations has intensified competition. This, combined with the hosts' reputational capital (Ikkala & Lampinen, 2014), necessitates maintaining high standards and adjusting pricing strategies (Lalicic & Weismayer, 2018).

Airbnb offers a diverse array of unique accommodations that promote well-being in stylish and inviting settings, catering to guests' desires for curiosity and new experiences. Consequently, Airbnb serves as a social alternative that facilitates an authentic exploration of the destination, enabling more efficient resource allocation.

On one hand, if we consider that the fundamental services may be comparable to those of a hotel (Tussyadiah & Zach, 2015), research focusing on the demand side of Airbnb reveals "a multiplicity of relevant motives, including economic, sustainability-related, and social aspects" (Dann, 2019).

Cheng and Jin (2019) suggest that Airbnb users may not prioritize value; however, competitive pricing (Balck & Cracau, 2015) and the physical attributes of accommodations (Dolnicar, 2019) remain conventional reasons for choosing peer-to-peer lodging over hotels (Quinby, 2014). Strømme-Bakhtiar and Vinogradov (2019) further emphasize that "Airbnb customers differ from traditional hotel patrons, as they [an extended family of more than five individuals] might not have considered visiting the location if the prices had not been favorable."

In addition to the economic advantages, the social or physical distance from other individuals, such as guests, may serve as a significant factor in the choice of peer-to-peer (P2P) accommodation, particularly when opting for entire apartments (Bresciani, 2021).

Mody (2017) assert that Airbnb surpasses traditional hotels in terms of community engagement and local authenticity, as it allows guests to stay in more residential neighborhoods and experience a genuine home-like atmosphere (Ert, 2016; Guttentag, 2015; Tussyadiah, 2015). Quattrone (2016) further suggest that P2P accommodation is expanding into residential zones and

is increasingly prevalent in areas lacking hotel options. Moreover, Airbnb properties offer a more genuine interactive experience compared to hotels (Birinci, 2018), which may foster customer loyalty (Grayson & Martinec, 2004, regarding their conceptualization of authenticity). Consequently, users of Airbnb are likely to appreciate the authentic environments surrounding their accommodations.

Guttentag (2018) illustrate that the elements of interaction and the benefits of home are fundamental to the Airbnb experience, which is characterized by authenticity rooted in enjoyment, escape, and the pursuit of novelty, as noted by Lalicic and Weismayer (2018). This aspect is considered more significant than the perceived risks involved. While Airbnb guests may encounter disappointments due to the shortcomings of amateur hosts—such as unsatisfactory personal interactions, inadequate cleanliness, or excessive noise—these factors can lead to negative evaluations of their stay (Gao, 2022). Nevertheless, authenticity remains a crucial component of hospitality experiences and is vital for ensuring guest satisfaction.

Gao (2022) assert that the host represents the second most prevalent topic and is the most significant characteristic distinguishing Airbnb from traditional hotels. Furthermore, earlier studies suggest that cultural exchange and social interaction with hosts play a vital role (Balck & Cracau, 2015; Guttentag, 2015; Wang & Nicolau, 2017). As noted by Bresciani (2021), “There is (indeed) a higher trust between guests and hosts.”

The amenities offered in P2P accommodations are recognized as pivotal elements that affect the satisfaction levels of Airbnb guests (Tussyadiah, 2016; Tussyadiah & Zach, 2015). These amenities play a significant role in shaping guests’ decision-making processes and enhancing their overall service experience (Sanchez-Franco & Alonso-Dos-Santos, 2021). Guests are particularly drawn to amenities that (a) provide a homely atmosphere as opposed to the experience of a traditional hotel, and (b) offer diverse experiences, with cost-effectiveness being a primary motivator alongside location and household features (Guttentag, 2018; Paulauskaite, 2017). For example, it has been noted that “males are focused on the importance of hygiene, quality or room amenities serving as surrogates for more comprehensive processing”. Consequently, the aspects related to the feeling of being at home are crucial for Airbnb guests (Ju, 2019).

Finally, Young (2017) establish that factors such as leisure travel, the size of the party, and the duration of the trip may serve as moderating influences in

the choice of peer-to-peer (P2P) accommodations, highlighting the significance of leisure travelers. Additionally, Airbnb is favored for trips taken with friends (Poon & Huang, 2017). For example, Airbnb accommodates a wide range of travel needs, from short day excursions to extended stays lasting several months, which often results in longer durations of stay for travelers (Tussyadiah, 2016), with the exception of business travelers (Varma, 2016).

Conclusion

Studies has identified both similarities and distinctions in the essential conditions required for generating satisfactory or unsatisfactory guest experiences in Airbnb accommodations compared to traditional hotels. While both types of lodging exhibit common issues leading to guest dissatisfaction—such as noise disturbances, perceived value for money, and the professionalism of staff—there are notable differences in the aspects they prioritize. For instance, Airbnb guests place a higher value on the proximity to tourist attractions and the quality of staff recommendations, whereas hotel guests tend to focus more on the available facilities and the professionalism of the staff. Additionally, Airbnb is known for providing unique and personalized experiences, while hotels emphasize the importance of efficient and appropriate interactions between staff and guests.

The implications of study findings are significant for hospitality providers aiming to enhance guest experiences and boost satisfaction and loyalty. By identifying and prioritizing the factors that influence guest satisfaction and dissatisfaction, hospitality managers can develop effective policies and strategies. Our study underscores the necessity of striking a balance between affordability and personalized experiences to elevate guest satisfaction. Furthermore, it suggests that hotels may need to integrate social and interpersonal elements into their services to maintain a competitive edge.

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